

Effect of maltose and hormones on callus formation and plant regeneration in isolated microspore culture of japonica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Microspore culture provides an ideal system for genetic manipulation in plants. Its efficiency in rice, however, is quite poor. We studied the effects of maltose, 2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D), and naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) on callus formation and plant regeneration from microspore culture of rice.

Three japonica cultivars and five liquid media were used (see table). The anthers with microspores at the middle to late uninucleate stage were pretreated at $6^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 17 d, then precultured onto liquid medium for another 5 d at $27^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. After that, the microspores were isolated from the anther with a glass rod

and washed with the same medium. The extract was filtered through a nylon sieve (100 μm pore size) and the filtrate was precipitated for 20 min, then centrifuged at $100 \times g$ for 2 min. The 2 ml of medium containing microspores in the bottom of the tube was cultured in petri dishes at a density of about 4.0×10^4 pollen grains/ml and kept in the dark at $27^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for callusing. Number of calli was recorded after 35 d.

Calli as large as 1.0-1.5 mm in diameter were transferred to medium of the same composition, solidified with 0.6% (w/v) agar. When calli became about 2 mm long, they were transferred to plant regeneration medium.

Only a few microspores in M1 and M2 media, which contained sucrose, divided without any callus formation. A high frequency of callus induction occurred, however, when microspores were cultured on media with maltose as the carbon source (Fig. 1a, b). All three genotypes responded well to the M3 medium, producing many calli. The frequency of callus formation could be raised by increasing the concentration of 2,4-D from

1. Strong expression of s band at sterile stage of TGMS and PGMS lines. 1-3: N422S; 6-8: Annong-1S; 4-5: Bodat Mayang (check).

2. S-band at four-leaf-old seedling stage of Annong-1S. 1-3: Annong-1S; 4-6: Annong-1 (check).

We used an improved method to conduct an esterase isozyme assay based on our prior work, adopting the discontinuous separating system. The staining method of M. Nakagahra was used.

Seven isozyme bands can be separated under our system of electrophoresis. We detected *Est-1* and *Est-2* isozyme bands at both the germinated seed stage and at all other growth stages and *Est-3* band at only the mature-leaf stage. A specific esterase band (s band) was discovered in Annong-1S and N422S, a photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) line derived from Nongken 58S (Fig. 1). Annong 1 and 210 other normal rice varieties did not have this s band. Its stable expression in mature leaves and unstable expression in young leaf blades are detectable in some PGMS and TGMS lines derived from Nongken 58S and Annong-1S (Fig. 2). We are conducting further studies on linkage analysis in segregating generations and its genetics. ■

a) Microspores started to divide after 5 d of culture (X60). b) Microcalli derived from microspore after 7-10 d of culture (X50). c) Green plantlet.

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Genotype	Callus induction medium ^a	Calli/anther (no.) ^b	Calli for regeneration (no.)	Plant regeneration ^c			
				Green		Albino	
				no.	%	no.	%
02428	M1	0	-	-	-	-	-
Xiushu 117	M1	0	-	-	-	-	-
Taipei 309	M1	0	-	-	-	-	-
02428	M2	0	-	-	-	-	-
Xiushu 117	M2	0	-	-	-	-	-
Taipei 309	M2	0	-	-	-	-	-
02428	M3	1.48	178	-	-	50	28.6
Xiushu 117	M3	1.38	145	1	0.7	-	-
Taipei 309	M3	1.24	269	26	9.7	63	23.4
Taipei 309	M4	1.66	155	9	5.8	35	22.6
Taipei 309	M5	0.46	148	18	12.2	69	46.6

^aM1 = MS salts + 100 mg/liter myoinositol + 1.0 mg/liter thiamine-HCl + 500 mg/liter glutamine + 0.5 mg/liter 2,4-D + 30 g/liter sucrose, pH 5.8; M2 = M1 + 30 g/liter sucrose; M3 = 60 g/liter maltose in place of 60 g/liter sucrose in M2; M4 = M3 + 0.5 mg/liter 2,4-D; M5 = M4 + 1.0 mg/liter NAA. ^bValues are means of three replications. ^cMS agar medium supplemented with 1 mg/liter vitamin B₁, 0.5 mg/liter vitamin B₆, 2 mg/liter glycine, 0.5 mg/liter nicotinic acid, 100 mg/liter myoinositol, 2 mg/liter kinetin, and 0.5 mg/liter indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), pH 5.8.

0.5 (M3) to 1.0 mg/liter (M4) callus induction medium (see table).

Green plant regeneration ranged from 0 to 12.2% and was greatly dependent on genotype; Taipei 309 was the most responsive (Fig. 1c). Although the callus formation per anther could be increased

with increased 2,4-D concentration from 1.24 (M3) to 1.66 (M4) mg/liter, most calli on M4 were smaller and more difficult to regenerate than those on M3. M5 had low callusing (0.46 per anther) but high regeneration capacity of green and albino plants. The results indicate

that the high frequency of callus induction and green plant regeneration from isolated microspore culture could be obtained by using maltose as a carbon source and 2,4-D and NAA as hormones in the induction medium. ■

Restorers and maintainers for four cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice

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We evaluated 84 hybrids, their pollen parents, and four isogenic maintainers (B lines) during Jul-Oct 1993 to identify maintainers and restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications. Each genotype was planted in three rows with 10 plants each at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha and other recommended cultural practices were followed.

Pollen fertility was determined from florets in the upper part of the panicles before dehiscence. Pollen grains were stained with IKI. Cultivars with <5% pollen fertility were classified as potential maintainers, those with 6-20% as partial maintainers, 21-95% as partial restorers, and >96% as potential restorers (see table).

We are using the maintainers identified in this experiment in a backcross program to develop new CMS lines. The restorers are being used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■

Improvement in anther culture of japonica/indica crosses of rice

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We conducted a study to generate an anther culture-derived population for use in molecular mapping of genes for cold

Restorers and maintainers for four CMS lines. Coimbatore, India. 1993.

CMS line	Potential maintainers	Partial maintainers	Partial restorers	Potential restorers
IR58025 A	Akinishiki, Pada-shabag, J. Samba (VTS), 03866, 03891, 03898, C29, C32, C33, Dular	ASD16 Kundalika, Black Puttu, Co 41, Basmati 370, C12, C19, C36	Oozora, IR50, AS781/5, ADT2, ADT36, Co 29, C15, C24, C37, C39, C40, C41	IR62, IR70, IR72, IR74, W. Ponni, AS781/3, AS781/1, AS781/4, TNAU831520, 03860, 03862, 03877, 03880, 03881, 04001, C1, C2, C6, C7, C10, C13, C20, C22, C35, C40
IR62829 A	—	TNAU88013, Zhuhio, TNAU841434, TNAU802293	Thalisamba, TNAU831520, IR20, Co 41, Co 29, Co 43, ASD18	Ponni, Co 44, C18, TNAU92093
V20 A	—	—	ASD18, Co 41	IR64, IR62, IR70, W. Ponni
MS37 A	—	TNAU89093, J. Samba (VTS)	TKM 6, ARC6650, Bhavani	IR62, IR42, Ponni, IR20

tolerance. Anther culture efficiency was studied in two F₁ hybrids, M201/IR50 and M202/IR50, and their respective parents. M201 and M202 are cold-tolerant japonicas and IR50 is a susceptible indica.

Anthers were pretreated at 9 °C for 7 d and were cultured in the dark on N6 callus induction medium supplemented with 6 g agarose/liter, 2 mg 2,4-D/liter and 60 g sucrose/liter. Plant regeneration from calli receiving no treatment (treatment 1) was compared with that

from calli subcultured three times each at biweekly intervals followed by a preculture treatment with abscisic acid (ABA) at 5 mg/liter (treatment 2). Regeneration medium (N6 medium, 2 mg kinetin/liter, 1 mg IAA/liter, and 1 mg NAA/liter) was similar for both treatments.

Callus induction and regeneration, regardless of treatments, followed the order of japonica>indica>japonica/indica. M201 recorded greater callusing (35%) and regeneration efficiency (1.2% in

Table 1. Callus induction in parents and F₁ crosses.

Genotype	Anthers plated (no.)	Anthers producing calli (no.)	Callus production before subculture ^a (%)
M201	720	252	35.0
M202	720	244	33.9
IR50	720	169	23.4
M201/IR50 (F ₁)	10836	1150	10.8
M303/IR50 (F ₁)	11880	1224	10.4
Total	24876	3039	12.2

$$^a = \frac{\text{Anthers producing calli}}{\text{Total anthers plated}} \times 100.$$